

Influence of *meta*- and *para*-Substituents on the Kinetics of Esterification of Phenoxyacetic Acids by Methanol

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The influence of *meta*- and *para*- substituents on the kinetics of acid-catalysed esterification of phenoxyacetic acids is discussed. In the case of *para* Cl, Br and I substituents, d-orbital resonance is suggested to explain the observed behaviour. The possibility of protonation of the methoxy oxygen in the acid medium employed is indicated to explain the slower rate of reaction of *m*- and *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetic acids.

In course of a study on the influence of substituents on the reactivity of benzene derivatives in which the reaction centre is not directly attached to the ring, we had occasion to observe the reactivities of several *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenoxyacetic acids in their acid-catalysed esterification. The interesting behaviour of some substituents is reported in this communication.

Experimental

All the phenoxyacetic acids were prepared by the method of Koelsch¹. Methanol was purified by the method of Lund and Bjerrum². The kinetic procedure followed was similar to that of Hartman and Borders³. The rate constants were calculated using Goldschmidt equation⁴

$$k = \frac{\left[(a+r) \ln \frac{a}{a-x} \right] - x}{rct}$$

where *a* is initial concentration of the organic acid, *x* is the concentration of the acid esterified in time *t*, *c* is the concentration of the acid catalyst and *r* is a factor which allows for the retardation of esterification by the water formed.

The initial concentration (*a*) of the organic acid was in the range 0.04 to 0.05*M* and the concentration (*c*) of the acid catalyst was around 0.008 *M*.

Results and Discussion

The relevant kinetic data for the esterification of *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenoxyacetic acids are given in Table 1. The behaviour of the halogeno acids may be seen to be of particular interest. Of the *m*-halogenophenoxyacetic acids, the fluoro compound has the highest rate even though it may be expected to react slowest by virtue of the greater -I effect of F compared to other halogeno substituents. In the same way the reactivities of the *para*-halogeno compounds also do not find a satisfactory explanation if we consider the -I and +M

TABLE 1—ESTERIFICATION OF SUBSTITUTED PHENOXYACETIC ACIDS

Substituent	10 ³ k(1 mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	
	30°	40°
H	2.96	6.10
<i>p</i> -F	2.62	4.95
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.26	4.39
<i>p</i> -Br	2.34	4.70
<i>p</i> -I	2.14	4.16
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.24	2.28
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	3.30	6.70
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	2.27	4.52
<i>p</i> -NH ₂ ⁺	1.20	2.17
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.55	3.04
<i>m</i> -Br	1.76	3.07
<i>m</i> -F	2.04	3.80
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	1.19	2.04
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	2.02	4.00
<i>m</i> -NH ₂ ⁺	1.89	2.57

effects of the halogeno substituents alone. These considerations suggest the operation of d-orbital resonance in the case of the chloro, bromo and iodo compounds. Mulliken⁵, Baliah⁶ and Goodman⁷ pointed out that halogens, excepting fluorine, have d-orbitals available in the valence shell for acceptor action and suggested the possibility that the net charge-release in a conjugated system is controlled by competition between the donor action of *pπ*- and the acceptor action of *dπ*-orbitals.

For the *p*-fluoro compound the opposed -I and +M effects are both considerable, the inductive effect outweighing the other slightly. For the other *p*-halogeno substituents, the net electron-withdrawing power (-I +M) may be greater than that for the *p*-fluoro substituent even though the -I and +M effects change in the order: F > Cl > Br > I. The jumbled order of *k* for the fluoro, chloro, bromo and iodo substituents as well as the observed highest electron-withdrawing power of the iodine substituent suggest the possibility of d-orbital resonance (I) being an important factor in understanding the behaviour of the halogeno substituents.

Normally, it is the inductive effect which determines the behaviour of the *meta*-substituents. If so, the *m*-fluoro compound should be the least reactive. But the observed order of reactivity ($m\text{-F} > m\text{-Br} > m\text{-Cl}$) is not so and suggests the interplay of different electronic effects.

The behaviour of *p*-methoxy group is also noteworthy. It is found to act as an electron-withdrawing substituent contrary to expectation. Considering the dissociation constants⁹ of phenoxyacetic acid and *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid we find that the latter is less acidic. The methoxy group of *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid is, therefore, electron-releasing. The fact that *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid undergoes acid-catalysed esterification at a slower rate than the unsubstituted acid indicates that the *p*-substituent in this reaction is electron-attracting. The slower rate of *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid compared to that of phenoxyacetic acid becomes understandable if we assume protonation of the methoxy group under the acidic condition of the reaction. In II, oxygen atom (1) is undoubtedly more basic than oxygen atom (2).

The protonated methoxyl group not only loses its ability to donate electrons, but acquires an increased electron-withdrawing inductive effect. The *m*-methoxy group may also be assumed to get protonated in this reaction although a *m*-methoxy group functions as an electron-withdrawing group⁸ even without such protonation. It may be of interest to note in this connection that *p*-anisic acid and 4-methoxy-1-naphthoic acid also react slower than their corresponding parent acids in acid-catalysed esterification⁶.

The rate-enhancing effect of the *p*-methyl group and the rate-retarding influence of the *p*- and *m*-nitro groups are as expected. With regard to *p*-aminophenoxyacetic acid, protonation of the amino group retards esterification.

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